

BENEFITS OF USING WEBQUESTS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *The article shows new ways in teaching foreign languages. Nowadays besides receiving foreign languages than native language, have become extremely beneficial. In the contemporary educational process teachers can use new technologies and forms of interaction with students and they are based on the intensification of independent activities and the direct participation of children in the educational process. WebQuest-technology is a new form of an educational organization, but it has some advantages and disadvantages in development of the active participation of the learners during the solution of search tasks.*

Keywords: *WebQuest technology, internet & website resources, a computer, a foreign language, pluses and minuses of the WebQuest, constructivism, speech, speaking skills, motivation, conversation, communication.*

INTRODUCTION

As more students gain access to the Internet, there is growing pressure on teachers to help their students use this valuable resource as an effective study tool. WebQuests are mini-projects in which a large percentage of the input and material is supplied by the Internet. WebQuests can be teacher-made or learner-made, depending on the learning activity the teacher decides on. Similarly, the Internet is one of the most important instruments of English language learning, teachers benefit from websites, because they help them master the methods and approaches of training. And students also benefit from websites, because they facilitate and expand the learning process focused on their knowledge.

METHODS

The Structure of Webquests recognized as the definitive schema for these activities - should only really be taken as a basic guideline and you should design

your WebQuests to suit the needs and learning styles of your students. There are usually four main sections to a WebQuest:

- The Introduction stage is normally used to introduce the overall theme of the WebQuest. It involves giving background information on the topic and, in the language learning context, often introduces key vocabulary and concepts which learners will need to understand in order to complete the tasks involved.

- The Task section of the WebQuest explains clearly and precisely what the learners will have to do as they work their way through the WebQuest. The task should obviously be highly motivating and intrinsically interesting for the learners, and should be firmly anchored in a real-life situation.

- The Process stage of a WebQuest guides the learners through a set of activities and research tasks, using a set of predefined resources. The Process stage of the WebQuest will usually have one (or sometimes several) 'products' which the learners are expected to present at the end. These 'products' will often form the basis of the Evaluation stage.

- The Evaluation stage can involve learners in self-evaluation, comparing and contrasting what they have produced with other learners and giving feedback on what they feel they have learnt, achieved, etc. It will also involve teacher evaluation of the same, and good WebQuests will give guidance to the teacher for this particular part of the process.

The use of computers in the learning process increases students' academic performance and motivates students to study together. Teachers are trying to use new strategies on their lessons, such as learning languages using a computer. Web Quest is a constructive training structure that uses links to worldwide web and other important resources. This is the real task - to encourage students to explore the central open question and take part in the solution.

RESULTS:

Web quests are one of the roots of a constructivist approach that allows research activities, which leads to an increase in their mental abilities. Many studies show that the Web Quest is very effective for the development of problem-solving skills, a high level of thinking and creativity, an increase in motivation, critical thinking and communication with content.

Using WebQuest as a pedagogical instrument is an effective and innovative way to use the Internet in learning process. Currently, students can communicate with each other and use computers as a valuable resource. Web quests are intended to ensure that students can choose the internet learning context. And Web Quest includes teamwork between groups of students to collect information and

access the Internet. WebQuest for teaching languages are used by many teachers of schools and universities around the world during their lessons for several years (March 2004)

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of WebQuests in education gives many advantages, helps to use time rationally, students use references to an effective search for information provided by the teacher. Another advantage of a web quest is supporting high-level of thinking.

Benefits of Web Quest

I. learners:

- Similar structure across WebQuests - Ease of use.
- Encourages readers to interact with information-based Internet resources.
- Motivating (stimulates learner's imagination)
- Students can create their own WebQuests (An engage with classmates' quest.)

- Web Quests can be worked on at home/library

II. Teachers:

- Similar structure in all Web Quests – Easy to create.
- Emphasis on teaching skills required to read Web Quests
- Encourages effective & structured use of Internet time (inquiry based lessons/units are designed so as to guide students meaningfully)
- Accommodates learners' diverse learning needs (individual and group work)

Negatives of web quest:

I. Learners:

- Most WebQuests are not designed to meet your specific state/provincial educational curriculum
- Access (slow web connectivity and inadequate number of computers)
- Resource links readability often too high
- Creating own WebQuest requires time upgrading technical skills and information literacy skills
- Inflexible structure

A speaking is defined as an interactive process of creating meaning, which includes the production, receipt and processing of information. And other scholars identified speaking as the production of hearing alarms causing various verbal reactions at the listeners. It is believed that it systematically combines the sounds for the formation of significant proposals. Another meaning of speaking is identified

as a bilateral process, including true transmission of opinions, information or emotions.

In order to solve these problems can be used WebQuests and to give students the opportunity to constructively learn and think critically. (Kundu and Bain, 2006). Most of the trainings can simply focus on the transfer of knowledge from the teacher. WebQuests allow students to play an active role in their knowledge, to rise communicative competence and increase their motivation towards the lessons. The method of constructivism includes functions like conducting complex open checks and providing students with opportunities in real, significant contexts to create their own hypotheses. In addition, the understanding of constructivism helps to create web quests.

There are factors affecting the performance of students in English. These factors play an important role in the development of students' spoken skills. Factors make students less confident in themselves, and students with higher motivation and less concern can easily and effectively speak. Thus, students should have a friendly and joint environment that can help them overcome difficulties in learning. Based on studying research literature, teachers need to understand the interests of their students, to strengthen students' confidence must choose the best learning method to keep participation in speech activities. They need to build friendly relations with their students. Teachers should expand the capabilities of their students to speak English, using some tasks that help them speak and encourage them to participate in a conversation. In addition, teachers should know when and how to correct the mistakes of students so that they are not afraid to make mistakes.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, we can highlight some reasons for using WebQuests There are many compelling reasons for using WebQuests in the classroom, including:

- They are an easy way for teachers to begin to incorporate the Internet into the language classroom, on both a short-term and long-term basis - no specialist technical knowledge is needed either to produce or use them.
- More often than not, they are group activities and as a result tend to lend themselves to communication and the sharing of knowledge - two principal goals of language teaching itself.
- They can be used simply as a linguistic tool, but can also be interdisciplinary, allowing for crossover into other departments and subject areas.

• They encourage critical thinking skills, including: comparing, classifying, inducing, deducing, analysing errors, constructing support, abstraction, analysing perspectives, etc. Learners are not able to simply regurgitate information they find, but are guided towards a transformation of that information in order to achieve a given task.

• They can be both motivating and authentic tasks and encourage learners to view the activities they are doing as something 'real' or 'useful'. This inevitably leads to more effort, greater concentration and a real interest in task achievement.

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